

Ion-exchange Equilibria of $\text{Na}^+ - \text{Ca}^{2+} / \text{Cl}^-$ and $\text{Na}^+ - \text{Mg}^{2+} / \text{Cl}^-$ from Concentrated Solution

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The ion exchange of alkaline earth metal ions from their concentrated mixtures with alkali metal ions is studied. It is observed that as the concentrations of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} in the solution increase, their uptake becomes smaller on the sodium form of Zeocarb-225. The no-selectivity line is reached when their concentrations reach 4.0 N.

THE behaviour of ions on exchange from concentrated solutions of $\text{Cu}^{2+} / \text{Na}^+$ on Dowex 50 $\times 8$ was found by Subbarao and David¹ to be different from that from dilute solutions. They observed that the selectivity of ions by this exchanger decreases in concentrated solutions. However, the extent of such a decrease in selectivity is not known for alkali/alkaline earth metal ions by synthetic resins.

Bokil² found that when schoenite, $\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, was added to soils with varying ion-exchange capacity e.g. red soil from Coimbatore, black soil from Bhavnagar and lateritic soil from Bangalore there was, in all cases, a reversal of uptake of Mg^{2+} beyond a certain concentration of schoenite and that K^+ was preferred by these clays. Hence we decided to inquire whether commercially available synthetic resins also show similar exchange behaviour in concentrated solutions.

We report here the results of our investigation on the behaviour of the strong acid exchanger, sodium form of zeokarb-225, from concentrated solutions of $\text{Na}^+ - \text{Ca}^{2+}$ and $\text{Na}^+ - \text{Mg}^{2+}$ as chlorides.

Experimental

Na-form of zeokarb-225 resin was equilibrated with the solution mixtures ($\text{Na}^+ / \text{M}^{2+}$ ratios 1 : 9 to 9 : 1) of chlorides of $\text{Na}^+ + \text{Ca}^{2+}$ and $\text{Na}^+ + \text{Mg}^{2+}$ of different concentrations (1.0 N to 4.0 N).

After 24 hr, the concentration of divalent ion was estimated by EDTA titration³ and fractions of metal ions in solutions and on the exchanger were calculated by difference. Results are given in Tables 1A and 1B. Equilibrium isotherms of $\text{Na}^+ - \text{Ca}^{2+}$ and $\text{Na}^+ - \text{Mg}^{2+}$ systems in three different concentrations (1.0, 2.0 and 4.0 N) were drawn by plotting equivalent ionic fractions of metal ions in

TABLE 1A— $\text{Na}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Mg}^{2+} (\text{Cl}^-)$ ION EXCHANGE EQUILIBRIA WITH ZEOKARB-225 AT $27 \pm 2^\circ$.

- (i) 25.0 ml 1.0 N mixture of 1.0 N NaCl + 1.0 N MgCl_2 + 1.0 g zeokarb-225 in Na^+ form.
(ii) 25.0 ml 2.0 N mixture of 2.0 N NaCl + 2.0 N MgCl_2 + 2.0 g zeokarb-225 in Na^+ form.
(iii) 25.0 ml 4.0 N mixture of 4.0 N NaCl + 4.0 N MgCl_2 + 4.0 g zeokarb-225 in Na^+ form.

Proportion of Na^+	Concentration of solns.	Fraction of Na^+ in solns.	Fraction of Na^+ on resin	Proportion of Na^+	Concentration of solns.	Fraction of Mg^{2+} in solns.	Fraction of Mg^{2+} on resin
Na_{10}	1.0 N	0.1995	0.088	Na_{10}	1.0 N	0.8005	0.9120
Na_{90}		0.3815	0.1754	Na_{90}		0.6185	0.8246
Na_{50}		0.5476	0.2608	Na_{50}		0.4524	0.7392
Na_{70}		0.7499	0.5069	Na_{70}		0.2500	0.4991
Na_{30}		0.9185	0.7730	Na_{30}		0.0815	0.2270
Na_{10}		0.1230	0.055	Na_{10}		0.8870	0.9450
Na_{10}	2.0 N	0.2268	0.1061	Na_{10}	2.0 N	0.7732	0.8939
Na_{90}		0.4137	0.2368	Na_{90}		0.5869	0.7614
Na_{50}		0.5923	0.4100	Na_{50}		0.4077	0.5900
Na_{70}		0.7398	0.5900	Na_{70}		0.2602	0.4100
Na_{30}		0.9101	0.8295	Na_{30}		0.0899	0.1705
Na_{10}		0.1279	0.0842	Na_{10}		0.8721	0.9158
Na_{10}	4.0 N	0.2103	0.2103	Na_{10}	4.0 N	0.7897	0.7895
Na_{90}		0.3899	0.4340	Na_{90}		0.6131	0.5660
Na_{50}		0.5608	0.5150	Na_{50}		0.4392	0.4850
Na_{70}		0.7464	0.7395	Na_{70}		0.2536	0.2665
Na_{30}		0.9114	0.9115	Na_{30}		0.0886	0.0885
Na_{10}		0.1205	0.1150	Na_{10}		0.8795	0.8850

Na_{10} means 10.0 ml of NaCl solution mixed with 90.0 ml of $\text{MgCl}_2 / \text{CaCl}_2$. Similarly for Na_{90} , Na_{50} , etc.

TABLE 1B—Na⁺⇌Ca²⁺(Cl⁻) ION EXCHANGE EQUILIBRIA WITH ZEOKARB-225.

Proportion of Na ⁺	Concentration of solns.	Fraction of Na ⁺ in solns.	Fraction of Na ⁺ on resin	Proportion of Na ⁺	Concentration of solns.	Fraction of Ca ²⁺ in solns.	Fraction of Ca ²⁺ on resin
(i) 25.0 ml 1.0 N mixture of 1.0 N NaCl + 1.0 N CaCl ₂ + 1.0 g zeokarb-225 in Na ⁺ form.	1.0 N	Na ₁₀	0.2065	0.0460	Na ₁₀	0.7935	0.9540
(ii) 25.0 ml 2.0 N mixture of 2.0 N NaCl + 2.0 N CaCl ₂ + 1.0 g zeokarb-225 in Na ⁺ form.		Na ₃₀	0.3689	0.1074	Na ₃₀	0.6311	0.8926
(iii) 25.0 ml 4.0 N mixture of 4.0 N NaCl + 4.0 N CaCl ₂ + 4.0 g zeokarb-225 in Na ⁺ form.		Na ₅₀	0.5622	0.2306	Na ₅₀	0.4378	0.7694
		Na ₇₀	0.7308	0.4054	Na ₇₀	0.2692	0.5946
		Na ₉₀	0.9095	0.6273	Na ₉₀	0.0905	0.3727
		Na ₀	0.1163	0.0269	Na ₀	0.8837	0.9731
1.0 N	2.0 N	Na ₁₀	0.2193	0.1384	Na ₁₀	0.7807	0.8616
		Na ₃₀	0.3995	0.2422	Na ₃₀	0.6005	0.7578
		Na ₅₀	0.5920	0.4070	Na ₅₀	0.4080	0.5930
		Na ₇₀	0.7381	0.5210	Na ₇₀	0.2619	0.4790
		Na ₉₀	0.9102	0.8335	Na ₉₀	0.0898	0.1665
		Na ₀	0.1309	0.0710	Na ₀	0.8691	0.9290
2.0 N	4.0 N	Na ₁₀	0.2103	0.2105	Na ₁₀	0.7897	0.7895
		Na ₃₀	0.3869	0.3340	Na ₃₀	0.6131	0.6660
		Na ₅₀	0.5608	0.5150	Na ₅₀	0.4392	0.4850
		Na ₇₀	0.7464	0.7235	Na ₇₀	0.2536	0.2765
		Na ₉₀	0.9166	0.8658	Na ₉₀	0.0834	0.1342
		Na ₀	0.1176	0.0955	Na ₀	0.8824	0.9045

solutions against equivalent ionic fractions of metal ions on exchanger and are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Na⁺⇌Mg²⁺ (Cl⁻) exchange isotherm for zeokarb-225 in Na⁺ form with 1.0, 2.0 and 4.0 N metal ion solutions at 27 ± 2°.

○ = Na⁺ ⊗ = Mg²⁺

Fig. 2. Na⁺⇌Ca²⁺ (Cl⁻) exchange isotherm for zeokarb-225 in Na⁺ form with 1.0, 2.0 and 4.0 N metal ion solutions at 27 ± 2°.

○ = Na⁺ ⊗ = Ca²⁺

Ca²⁺ on the exchanger is also found to decrease as 0.9731, 0.9290 and 0.9045 meq with the respective concentrations of solution of Mg²⁺.

It can be seen from the results in Table 1A that fraction of Na⁺ on the resin from MgCl₂ solution is 0.055, 0.0842 and 0.1150 meq, respectively with the 1.0, 2.0 and 4.0 N metal ion concentrations. Similarly, corresponding fraction of Mg²⁺ on resin is 0.9455, 0.9158 and 0.8850 meq from 1.0, 2.0 and 4.0 N metal ion concentrations. The fraction of

Thus, both Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ are exchanged on resins to a lesser extent from more concentrated solutions. The difference between the exchange of Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ on the resin is small, Ca²⁺ being exchanged to a slightly greater extent. Thus, a striking fact emerges that both Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ are exchanged less and less from concentrated solutions.

It can, therefore, be stated that a greater concentration of a bivalent ion results in lower exchange of that ion.

The decreasing exchange of bivalent metal ions by sodium form of zeokarb-225 from their increasingly more concentrated solutions can be explained on the following two grounds⁴.

(1) *Donnan equilibrium* : The Donnan potential set up by a resin is directly proportional to the ionic molality in the resin and is inversely proportional to the solution concentration. Thus, with large concentrations, the Donnan potential driving the counter ion into the resin is weaker. This results in a lower exchange from concentrated solutions.

(2) *Ion-pair formation* : In concentrated solutions, dissociation of a salt into ions becomes smaller. Ion-pairs are found to be present in an increasingly larger amount as the concentration of the electrolyte increases⁵. The ion-pair formation is greater in ions of larger valency. Hence Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} ions form ion-pairs to a greater extent than alkali metals.

Equilibrium isotherms, which are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 suggest that as the concentration of the solution increases, the uptake of bivalent metal ions on the Na^+ form of the exchanger decreases. At about 4.0 N concentration of equilibrated solution, the equilibrium isotherms tend to coincide with the line of zero-selectivity showing thereby that the exchanger has practically no preference

for either the bivalent or the monovalent cations. Between Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} is preferred to a slightly greater extent. This is because, as the concentration increases and the water activity falls, Ca^{2+} begins to gradually lose its hydration and tends to go into the resin phase and is found to be preferred⁶ to Mg^{2+} . This effect, however, is very small as far as Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} are concerned.

It can be deduced from the above data obtained by batch experiments that in column operation, the conversion of the resin from the monovalent to the bivalent metal form (i.e. exhaustion cycle) can be achieved very well by employing dilute solutions of the bivalent metal ion concerned, whereas the regeneration cycle i.e. conversion of the exchanger from bivalent to monovalent form can be achieved by the use of concentrated solution of monovalent ions. Dilute solutions of such monovalent ions will also be more effective for the regeneration cycle.

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